

Capturing Non-linear Neighbourhood Structure: An Autoencoder Approach to Census-based Dimensionality Reduction

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Summary

Dimensionality reduction underpins geodemographic analysis, yet traditional linear methods like PCA inadequately capture non-linear relationships in spatial socio-economic data. We evaluate the effectiveness of autoencoders as a practical alternative for deriving composite neighbourhood measures from census data. Using 408 variables from the 2021 England and Wales Census across 188,880 Output Areas, we demonstrate autoencoders achieve 19.4% lower reconstruction error than PCA at typical operational dimensions. Improvements are greatest in deprived and demographically complex areas where PCA systematically underperforms. Autoencoders offer parametric projection of new areas, reconstruction-based diagnostics, and reduced parameter sensitivity.

KEYWORDS: Autoencoders, Dimensionality reduction, Geodemographics, Census data, Neighbourhood classification

Introduction

Dimensionality reduction is fundamental to spatial data analysis, enabling researchers to distil high-dimensional measures into compact representations suitable for mapping, modelling, and policy applications. Traditional approaches such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) have long served as the methodological backbone for deriving composite measures of neighbourhood structure, underpinning influential frameworks from Social Area Analysis (Shevky and Williams, 1949; Shevky and Bell, 1955) to contemporary geodemographic classifications (Harris, Sleight and Webber, 2005; Singleton and Spielman, 2014; Batey, 2022). However, linear methods such as PCA rest on assumptions that may inadequately capture the complex, non-linear dependencies characteristic of spatial socio-economic data.

The limitations of linear dimensionality reduction in geographical contexts have been recognised since the critiques of Factorial Ecology in the 1970s and 1980s (Hughes and Carey, 1972; Hunter, 1972; Johnston, 1977; Vies, 1978). Geographic phenomena frequently produce nonlinear dependencies, interaction terms, and threshold effects in spatial datasets that PCA's orthogonal linear components cannot adequately capture.

While manifold-learning methods such as t-SNE (Maaten and Hinton, 2008), UMAP (Healy and McInnes, 2024), Kernel PCA (Schölkopf, Smola and Müller, 1998), and Diffusion Maps (Coifman and Lafon, 2006) offer principled approaches to capturing non-linear structure, their non-parametric nature introduces operational constraints for applied neighbourhood analysis. These methods typically lack natural mechanisms for projecting new observations without complete reprocessing, provide limited reconstruction diagnostics for assessing information preservation, and require careful

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parameter tuning that may vary across geographic contexts. Although parametric variants have been proposed (Maaten, 2009; Sainburg, McInnes and Gentner, 2021), these remain less widely adopted.

This paper demonstrates that autoencoders (AEs) are effective and practical as a non-linear parametric alternative for deriving composite measures of neighbourhood structure from census data.

Autoencoders offer powerful unsupervised dimensionality-reduction frameworks (Wang, Yao and Zhao, 2016), pairing an encoder that compresses inputs into a low-dimensional latent space with a decoder that reconstructs the original data (Rezende, Mohamed and Wierstra, 2014; Kingma and Welling, 2019). Prior work points to their utility for geodemographic preprocessing and classification (De Sabbata and Liu, 2019; 2023), geographic embeddings (Cepeda, Nayak and Shah, 2023; Agarwal et al., 2024), and built-environment analysis from satellite imagery (Singleton et al., 2022; Klemmer et al., 2024). We evaluate the approach using small-area data from the 2021 Census of England and Wales, comparing how effectively AEs summarise spatial variability and reveal composite dimensions of residential differentiation relative to PCA.

2. Methodological Framework

2.1 Data and Study Area

Input data were extracted from the 2021 England and Wales Census at the Output Area (OA) scale, which is the smallest unit for which census data are disseminated in the UK, typically comprising 40–250 households. The data encompassed 188,880 OAs across England and Wales. Variables were drawn from topics including Demography and Migration, Ethnicity, Identity, Language and Religion, Work and Travel, Housing, Education, and Health. After excluding variables with limited geographic coverage (Welsh language, short-term non-UK residents, second home type) and removing population density, 408 variables remained, all expressed as percentages relative to appropriate denominators.

2.2 Autoencoder Architecture

The autoencoder comprises an encoder that compresses input data into a compact latent representation and a decoder that reconstructs original data from this compressed form (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Model Encoder Decoder Architecture

Unlike PCA, which finds global linear axes maximising variance, autoencoders learn hierarchical features through stacked layers of non-linear transformations, enabling them to capture complex interactions and context-dependent patterns. Our architecture employs three dimensionality-reducing layers, each followed by Leaky ReLU activation functions introducing non-linearity. Layer sizes decrease linearly from the 408-dimensional input to the bottleneck dimension (Table 1). The model was trained using normalised mean squared error (MSE) loss with the AdamW optimiser, implementing a mini-batch approach (1% random subsets per epoch) for stable gradient updates. Models were trained for 500 epochs across bottleneck dimensions ranging from 2 to 128.

To assess training stability, we trained each model configuration ten times with different random initialisations. The models were trained on a pair of A6000 Nvidia GPU utilising Pytorch and Pytorch Lightning, with CUDA enabled. Each model trained in under 10 minutes with a storage footprint under 2 MB.

Parameter	Parameter Setting
Bottleneck dimensionality (B)	2, 4, 6, 8, 16, 32, 64, 100, 128
Architecture	Symmetric, 3 hidden layers (D1, D2, D3)
Hidden layer sizes	Linear interpolation from 408 to B
Hidden activation	LeakyReLU ($\alpha = 0.01$)
Optimiser	AdamW ($\text{lr} = 10^{-3}$, weight decay = 10^{-2})
LR schedule	ReduceLROnPlateau (factor = 0.2, patience = 10)
Loss function	Normalised MSE
Epochs	500
Batch size	1% of observations
Random seed	$20210321 + (i \times 1000)$ for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, 9\}$

Table 1: Autoencoder Parameter Settings

2.3 Evaluation Framework

We assessed AE performance against PCA through multiple approaches: (i) overall reconstruction accuracy measured by root mean squared error (RMSE); (ii) spatial structure of reconstruction errors using Global Moran's I and (iii) error distribution across socio-economic gradients (Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD), population density).

3. Results

3.1 Reconstruction Accuracy

The autoencoder consistently outperforms PCA in reconstruction accuracy across nearly all tested bottleneck dimensions (Figure 2). At 100 dimensions, PCA achieves RMSE of 0.943% while the AE achieves 0.826%, representing a 19.4% relative improvement. This demonstrates that meaningful non-linear relationships exist within neighbourhood-level census data that linear methods fail to capture. The performance gap is most pronounced at lower dimensions where compression is greatest. At two dimensions, the AE RMSE is 3.8% compared to PCA's 5.45%, a 28.9% relative improvement. As the latent dimensionality approaches that of the original input data, the advantage of nonlinear methods diminishes: with minimal compression, there is less complex structure for the autoencoder to exploit, and both methods converge toward near-perfect reconstruction.

Figure 2: A comparison of the reconstruction error between PCA and autoencoder methods as a function of compressed latent space dimensionality. Autoencoder results represent the mean RMSE over ten independent training runs, with between-run variability too small to be visible at this scale.

3.2 Spatial Structure of Errors

Both methods produce reconstruction errors with significant spatial autocorrelation (all Moran's I p-values < 0.001), though AE errors exhibit consistently lower spatial clustering. At 100 dimensions, PCA errors show Moran's I of 0.494 compared to AE's 0.474, suggesting the autoencoder captures spatially-varying patterns more effectively, leaving less systematic spatial structure in residuals.

3.3 Error Distribution Across Socio-Economic Gradients

Reconstruction errors are systematically higher in more deprived and densely populated areas for both methods, but the autoencoder substantially reduces these disparities (Figure 3). For PCA, error in the most deprived IMD decile is 31.8% higher than in the least deprived; for AE, this differential reduces to 29.9%. Similarly, the density gradient shows 45.7% higher error in the densest versus least dense deciles for PCA, compared to 43.3% for AE.

Figure 3: Reconstruction Error distribution by IMD decile (1 most deprived, 10 least deprived) and population density decile (1 most dense, 10 least dense). The dashed line indicates the average improvement across all deciles.

Crucially, the largest relative improvements occur in areas within the most deprived and highest density deciles. This suggests autoencoders not only improve overall accuracy but help mitigate systematic biases in how different neighbourhood types are represented.

4. Geographic Patterns

Mapping reconstruction errors reveals clear spatial patterns (Figure 4). Urban areas consistently show higher errors, reflecting their demographic complexity. However, distinctive rural outliers appear in PCA results, particularly in Cornwall and North Wales, where poor reconstruction of national identity variables contributes significantly to error. Cornish and Welsh identities exhibit non-linear relationships with other census variables that PCA fails to capture but AE handles more effectively.

Figure 4: The mean reconstruction error for each MSOA in England and Wales for; (a) the PCA reconstruction with 100 components, and (b) the Autoencoder reconstruction error with a bottleneck dimension of 100.

AE has a lower RMSE than PCA for all 7,264 MSOAs, indicating that AE outperforms PCA almost universally. The largest improvements concentrate in dense urban centres (e.g., central Leeds with high international student populations), previously identified outlier regions (Cornwall), and areas with transient populations including Royal Air Force bases.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

This study establishes that autoencoders can improve performance relative to traditional linear dimensionality reduction techniques for deriving composite measures of neighbourhood structure. The consistent 19.4% improvement in reconstruction accuracy at typical operational dimensions, combined with reduced systematic biases across socio-economic gradients and neighbourhood types, demonstrates substantial analytical advantages.

The pronounced improvements in complex urban environments and demographically diverse areas have significant implications for applied research. If composite measures systematically underperform in particular contexts, downstream analyses may produce spatially biased results affecting policy interventions and resource allocation. Autoencoders' more consistent performance across geographic contexts offers potential for more equitable analytical frameworks.

Among nonlinear approaches, three key advantages position AEs for geodemographic applications: (i) parametric encoding enables projection of new areas without recomputing existing embeddings; (ii) decoder reconstruction enables transparent diagnostics quantifying information preservation; and (iii) learned representations reduce reliance on fragile hand-tuned parameters. While challenges remain, particularly regarding interpretability relative to PCA loadings and computational requirements, the demonstrated benefits suggest non-linear approaches merit serious consideration for future geodemographic research where accurate representation of neighbourhood diversity is essential.

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Biographies

Owen Goodwin is a Senior Data Scientist at the Geographic Data Service and University of Liverpool. He holds a PhD in experimental particle physics from the University of Manchester. His research develops data science and machine learning methods for large-scale geographic datasets, with current projects on geodemographic classification and retail centre delineation.

Alex Singleton is Professor of Geographic Information Science at the University of Liverpool and Director of the Geographic Data Service. His research sits at the boundary between the social and computational sciences; and has extended a tradition of area classification within Urban Analytics where he has developed an empirically informed critique of the ways in which geodemographic methods (unsupervised machine learning) can be refined for effective yet ethical use; and how systems comprising artificial intelligence can assist in public resource allocation applications. This

research has developed from substantive interests around the social, spatial and temporal dimensions of urban systems; specifically focused on inequalities of opportunities.

Stef De Sabbata is an Associate Professor of Geographical Information Science at the School of Geography, Geology and the Environment and Senior Fellow at the Institute for Digital Culture of the University of Leicester. She is the Chair of the Geographic Information Science Research Group of the Royal Geographical Society with IBG and part of the steering committee of GIScience Research UK (GISRUK). Her research focuses on geospatial artificial intelligence (GeoAI), including the development of spatially-explicit approaches to urban analytics, including foundation models. Her work also includes the study of the geospatial mechanistic interpretability of large language models and the application of generative artificial intelligence in geography and cultural analytics.